

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF LANTHANIDE COMPLEXES WITH AMINO ACIDS

Temp. = 25°, Ionic strength = 0.2 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand	Formation constant*	La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}	Gd ^{III}
Glycine	log K_1	4.09	4.42	4.40	4.50	5.14	4.64
	log K_2	3.49	3.52	3.74	4.12	4.34	4.53
α -Alanine	log K_1	3.76	4.29	4.57	4.80	5.10	5.18
	log K_2	3.43	3.49	4.00	3.60	4.09	4.23
Leucine	log K_1	4.59	5.03	5.25	4.93	5.39	5.21
	log K_2	4.04	3.91	4.23	3.75	3.99	4.31
Isoleucine	log K_1	4.22	5.48	4.93	5.24	5.35	5.21
	log K_2	3.52	3.77	4.06	3.99	4.37	4.60

* limits of error, $\pm 0.02 - 0.09$ in log scale.

amount of metal nitrate, were prepared. Total volume of each solution was 50 ml. All the solutions were pH-metrically titrated with a standard 0.2 M NaOH solution using a Elico LI-10 G pH meter at 25°. From the titration data $\bar{n}_H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated as described earlier⁴. Metal-ligand formation constants were calculated by the procedure of Irving-Rossotti^{5,6}. Results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The formation constants of trivalent lanthanide-amino acid complexes were found to be in the order, La < Ce < Pr < Nd < Sm > Gd. Steady increase in log K_1 values from La^{III} to Sm^{III} is the result of decrease of size of the M³⁺ ions with subsequent increase in ionic potential. The decrease in ionic size of lanthanide ions is not regular, the biggest decrease is being observed with the first electron added to each orbital *i.e.* in cases of Ce^{III}, Pr^{III} and Nd^{III}. Besides this, the charge-size ratio also increases from La^{III} to Gd^{III}. It is observed that higher the values of charge-size ratio, greater is the stability of the complexes.

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Equilibrium Studies on the Formation of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Mercury(II) in Solution

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MERCURY(II) compounds possess varying degree of toxicity^{1,2}. The toxic behaviour of the complexes besides other factors is probably dependent on the stability and geometry of the various complex species. The literature survey indicates extensive research work on the determination of stability of binary complexes especially with amines, amino acids and sulphur containing ligands³. However, similar investigations on mixed ligand complexes are less comprehensive^{4,5}, and only a few ternary systems have been studied.

Equilibrium studies on the following MAL type complexes of Hg^{II} have been carried out: A. (i) Hg^{II}Cl-dien; B. (i) Hg^{II}-dien/amine, (ii) Hg^{II}Cl-dien/amine; C. (i) Hg^{II}-dien/amino acid, (ii) Hg^{II}Cl-dien/amino acid. Diethylenetriamine (dien) was considered as the primary ligand and an amine, *i.e.* ethylenediamine (en), 2-amino-ethanol (2-amath), amino acid *i.e.* glycine (gly), L-lysine (lys), L-histidine (hist), DL-alanine (alan), glutamic acid (glu) and L-cysteine (cyst) were considered as the secondary ligand. The stepwise stability constants were evaluated at two different temperatures, *viz.* 30 and 45 $\pm$ 0.01° at 0.1 M ionic strength (with respect to KNO₃). With the help of the stabilities evaluated at two different temperatures, the thermodynamic parameters namely ΔF° , ΔH° and ΔS° were calculated. The titrations have been carried out employing Bjerrum-Calvin's pH-titration technique.

Experimental

Diethylenetriamine (dien) (Pfaltz and Baker) was dried over potassium hydroxide and distilled.

The solution was standardised potentiometrically. All other chemicals, glycine (98.5%, B.D.H.), 2-amino-ethanol (Riedel-De-Haenag), DL-alanine (B.D.H.), glutamic acid (99%, E. Merck), L-cysteine (SD's) were used without further purification. The solutions of the samples were prepared in double-distilled water.

Preparation of 1:1 Hg(dien)(ClO₄)₂: The complex was prepared by mixing freshly prepared solution of mercuric perchlorate with the solution of dien (3.433 g in minimum amount of water). The reaction mixture was shaken well and then cooled in an ice-bath for 2 h. The resulting crystals were filtered, washed with cold water and ethanol, and finally dried at 40° in an oven. The results of mercury analysis and ir are given below. Mercuric perchlorate solution was prepared by treating a solution of mercuric chloride (9.50 g) with excess of 2 M NaOH and washing the precipitate several times by decantation. The precipitated mercuric oxide was dissolved in minimum amount of warm 1:1 perchloric acid, and the solution filtered quantitatively with a few washings. The characteristics of the complex are as follows: white crystalline, soluble in hot water; Hg, 39.20% (calcd. 39.90); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 310 and 3 250 cm⁻¹ (NH₂).

In the case of dien, the NH bond stretching frequency peak is a broad one but appears as two peaks at 3 320 and 3 260 cm⁻¹ which is obviously due to the presence of two types of NH frequencies arising out of NH₂ (3 320 cm⁻¹) and NH (3 260 cm⁻¹). The ir spectra of the amine complex shows that bands corresponding to NH₂ shift to lower frequencies, which indicates that mercury is coordinated through nitrogen atoms of the amine ligand.

Titration procedure: The stabilities of MA and MAL type complexes have been evaluated by the pH titration technique of Bjerrum⁶ as modified by

Irving and Rossotti⁷. The following three reaction mixtures were prepared to study the Hg^{II}Cl-dien simple system as well as the Hg^{II}/Hg^{II}Cl-dien/amine/amino acid mixed ligand systems. Hg^{II}-Cl-dien, simple system: A. 0.5 M KNO₃ 10.0 ml + 0.1 M HNO₃ 5.0 ml; B. 0.5 M KNO₃ 10.0 ml + 0.1 M HNO₃ 5.0 ml + primary ligand (0.01 M) 10.0 ml; C. 0.5 M KNO₃ 10.0 ml + 0.1 M HNO₃ 5.0 ml + primary complex solution (0.01 M) 10.0 ml. Hg^{II}/Hg^{II}Cl-dien/amine/amino acid mixed ligand systems: A. 0.5 M KNO₃ 10.0 ml + 0.1 M HNO₃ 5.0 ml; B. 0.5 M KNO₃ 10.0 ml + 0.1 M HNO₃ 5.0 ml + secondary ligand (0.01 M) 10.0 ml; C. 0.5 M KNO₃ 10.0 ml + 0.1 M HNO₃ 5.0 ml + secondary ligand (0.01 M) 10.0 ml + primary complex solution (0.01 M) 10.0 ml. The total volume in all cases was raised to 50 ml containing 10% ethanol. The solutions were titrated with a standard solution of alkali at two different temperatures, 30 and 45°. The solutions were kept for at least 30 min in a thermostat for attainment of the requisite temperature.

Calculations: From the titration curves using the solutions A and B, the horizontal distance between the curves at different pH values was used for calculating $\bar{n}_H$ (average number of protons attached to the ligand). Similarly, $\bar{n}$ values have been evaluated by measuring horizontal difference in volume of alkali required to produce the same pH in the metal and ligand titrations for reaction mixtures B and C. After calculating $\bar{n}_H$ and $\bar{n}$ values, the pK values were calculated. Finally, $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of metal complex ion equilibria. From the formation curves log K values were evaluated by half $\bar{n}$ method. The stepwise stability constants alongwith ΔF° , ΔH° and ΔS° values are given in Tables 1-4.

TABLE 1—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1:1:1 TERNARY Hg^{II} Cl COMPLEXES
Ionic strength=0.1 M (KNO₃)

MAL system	30°		45°		ΔH° kcal mol ⁻¹	30° ΔS° cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	log K	$-\Delta F^\circ$ kcal mol ⁻¹	log K	$-\Delta F^\circ$ kcal mol ⁻¹		
Hg ^{II} Cl-dien	11.0	15.25	11.47	16.69	13.82	95.94

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1:1:1 TERNARY Hg^{II} COMPLEXES
Ionic strength=0.1 M (KNO₃)

MAL system	30°		45°		ΔH°	30° ΔS° cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	log K ^{MAL} _{MA}	$-\Delta F^\circ$ kcal mol ⁻¹	log K ^{MAL} _{MA}	$-\Delta F^\circ$ kcal mol ⁻¹		
Hg ^{II} (dien)-(en)	8.80	12.20	7.45	10.84	-99.70	-90.76
Hg ^{II} (dien)-(dien)	7.35	10.19	7.63	11.10	8.24	60.83
Hg ^{II} (dien)-(2-amath)	5.00	6.93	3.30	4.80	-50.00	-142.15
	log K ^{MAL} _{MACl}	$-\Delta F^\circ$	log K ^{MAL} _{MACl}	ΔF°	ΔH°	ΔS°
Hg ^{II} (dien)-(en)	6.51	9.03	6.50	9.46	-0.29	28.84
Hg ^{II} (dien)-(dien)	5.95	8.25	6.95	10.11	29.41	124.29
Hg ^{II} (dien)-(2-amath)	4.55	6.31	4.82	7.01	7.94	47.03

NOTES

TABLE 3—METAL—LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1 : 1 : 1 TERNARY HgII COMPLEXES
Ionic strength = 0.1 M (KNO₃)

MAL system	30°		45°		ΔH° kcal mol ⁻¹	30° ΔS° cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	log K _{MA} ^{MAL}	-ΔF° kcal mol ⁻¹	log K _{MA} ^{MAL}	-ΔF° kcal mol ⁻¹		
HgII (dien)-(gly)	6.95	8.80	6.00	8.73	-10.29	-4.92
HgII (dien)-(lys)	5.95	8.25	5.50	8.80	-13.24	-16.47
HgII (dien)-(hist)	4.12	5.71	4.57	6.65	-13.24	-62.54
HgII (dien)-(alan)	6.97	8.83	6.73	9.75	10.59	64.09
HgII (dien)-(glu)	6.91	8.75	6.02	8.76	-8.53	0.73
HgII (dien)-(cyst)	4.47	6.20	4.92	7.16	13.24	64.16

TABLE 4—METAL—LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1 : 1 : 1 TERNARY HgII COMPLEXES
Ionic strength = 0.1 M (KNO₃)

MAL system	30°		45°		ΔH° kcal mol ⁻¹	30° ΔS° cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	log K _{MACl} ^{MAL}	ΔF° kcal mol ⁻¹	log K _{MACl} ^{MAL}	ΔF° kcal mol ⁻¹		
HgII (dien)-(gly)	5.48	7.60	5.44	8.21	4.71	40.63
HgII (dien)-(lys)	5.40	7.63	6.75	9.82	36.76	146.50
HgII (dien)-(hist)	4.90	5.96	4.85	7.06	16.13	73.07
HgII (dien)-(alan)	5.95	7.42	5.45	7.93	2.94	34.19
HgII (dien)-(glu)	5.84	8.10	6.33	9.21	14.41	74.29
HgII (dien)-(cyst)	5.70	7.90	5.45	7.93	-7.35	1.82

Results and Discussion

A. *Hg^{II}Cl-dien complex, simple system*: Diethylenetriamine is completely protonated in the reaction mixture in presence of strong acid, and on titrating with alkali the deprotonation takes place. The protonation constant values of dien have already been reported by Smith and Martell. On titrating with alkali the deprotonation starts, and with increase of pH the concentration of the free ligand increases which then combines with the metal salt to form MACl complex, primary complex according to the equation,

where, L is the free amine. A perusal of Table 2 indicates that log K_{MA}^{MAL} values are generally higher than the log K_{MACl}^{MAL} values. The reason for this may be that in the former case a five- or six-coordinate species is formed from three-coordinate species, while in the latter case the five- or six-coordinate species is derived from a four-coordinate species.

A perusal of Table 1 indicates that with increase of temperature the free energy has more negative value. The entropy term is positive and overrides the unfavourable enthalpy term. Therefore, the entropy term favours complex formation.

B. *Hg^{II}/Hg^{II}Cl-dien/en, dien/2-amath mixed ligand systems*: The sequence of deprotonation of protonated amines and the pK₁, pK₂ and pK₃ values have already been reported by Smith and Martell. When the reaction mixture containing the MA/MACl complex and the secondary ligand in the ratio of 1 : 1 is titrated with standard alkali, the deprotonation of amines takes place and the concentration of free amines increases which then combines with the MA/MACl complex to form MAL mixed ligand complex according to the equation,

C. *Hg^{II}/Hg^{II}Cl-dien/amino acid mixed ligand systems*: The protonation constant values of various amino acids have already been reported by Smith and Martell. A perusal of Table 3 indicates that log K_{MA}^{MAL} values are generally higher than the corresponding values of log K_{MACl}^{MAL}. However, perusal of Table 4 reveals that for the mixed ligand systems of L-histidine and L-cysteine, the log K_{MACl}^{MAL} values are higher as compared to values of log K_{MA}^{MAL} for the same systems as shown in Table 3. It may be attributed to the formation of MAClL species through an additional equilibrium. For the mixed ligand systems of glycine, L-lysine and glutamic acid (Table 3) and L-cysteine (Table 4), the negative enthalpy term which is higher in magnitude as compared to the unfavourable entropy term, strongly favours complex formation. Therefore,

the overall free energy change is due to favourable enthalpy term. Tables 3 and 4 also reveal that for all other mixed ligand systems, the entropy term is positive and overweighs the unfavourable enthalpy term. Therefore, the overall free energy change is due to favourable entropy term.

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Kinetics of Oxidation of *o*-Cresol by Cerium(IV) in Acidic Medium

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ALTHOUGH hexacyanoferrate(III)¹, vanadium(V)² peroxodisulphate(II) ion³, lead(IV) acetate⁴, IO₄⁻(I)⁵ have been employed as oxidants for the oxidation of organic compounds, yet similar studies on the oxidation of *o*-cresol by cerium(IV) are lacking. This communication describes the kinetics of the oxidation of *o*-cresol by ceric ion.

Experimental

For purification, *o*-cresol (AnalaR) was refluxed with zinc dust and ceric sulphate was recrystallised. *o*-Cresol was dissolved in aqueous acetone (50%, v/v), while ceric sulphate was dissolved in 2 M H₂SO₄. The kinetics of the process was measured by measuring the optical density at 380 nm on a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. The overall order of reaction was evaluated from Fig. 1, while order with respect to each reactant was evaluated from Figs. 2 and 3.

Results and Discussion

Ionic strength dependence: The plot of k vs $\mu^{1/2}$ (Fig. 4) comes out to be linear, which shows a negative and primary exponential type of salt effect.

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Fig. 1. Second order rate constant for the oxidation of *o*-cresol by Ce^{IV}; initial concentrations of both *o*-cresol and Ce^{IV} are (I) 5.0 × 10⁻⁴, (II) 7.5 × 10⁻⁴, (III) 10.0 × 10⁻⁴, and (IV) 12.5 × 10⁻⁴ M, at 30°.

Fig. 2. Effect of concentration of Ce^{IV} on the oxidation of *o*-cresol by Ce^{IV}, concentration of *o*-cresol is 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, and concentrations of Ce^{IV} being (I) 2.0 × 10⁻³, (II) 4.0 × 10⁻³, (III) 6.0 × 10⁻³ and (IV) 8.0 × 10⁻³ M, at 30°.

This indicates that the rate determining step involves the interaction of two ions of the opposite charges.

The reaction rate increases with increasing acid concentration. Allyl alcohol, allyl acetate and EDTA act as radical traps.

Thermometric parameters: The energy of activation (ΔE^*), frequency factor (A), free energy